

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF AN SMART ELECTRICITY BILL
PAYMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
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DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF AN SMART ELECTRICITY BILL PAYMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Abstract

The project is a web based application where users can get instant electricity bill and pay them online via credit card. The system automates the conventional process of paying electricity bill by visiting the place. Users have to stand in queue for paying bill and wait for their turn. The process is tiresome and time consuming. They even have to wait for the bill being delivered to their place which sometimes can be delivered late by the delivery boy. Hence the system is developed to automate the electricity bill calculation and payment for user convenience.

The system would be having two logins admin and user login. Admin can view user account details and can even add or updates things in their account. Admin has to feed the system with electricity usage data into respective users account. The system then calculates the electricity bill for every user and updates the information into their account every month. User can view their electricity bill and then the user can get the information like how voltages are used in individual home appliances. Then the system is used to calculate the voltage level of particular home appliance and how much of cost is used in that particular appliance and also individually pay on the spot before month end. If user is incapable of paying the bill before month end, it then calculates fine for each day.

INTRODUCTION

Electricity is one of the vital requirements for sustainment of comforts of life. IT should be used very judiciously for its proper utilization. But in our country we have lot of localities where we have surplus supply for the electricity while many areas do not even have access to it. Our policies of its distribution are also partially responsible for this because we are still not able to correctly estimate our exact requirements and still how much of power units are used at a particular home appliances is prevailing.

On the other hand consumers are also not satisfied with the services of power companies. Most of the time they have complaints regarding statistical errors in their monthly bills. Thus we are trying to present an idea towards the minimization of technical errors and to reduce human dependency at the same time. With the help of this project we are aiming to receive the monthly energy consumption from a remote location directly to a centralized office. In this way we can reduce human efforts needed to record the meter readings which are till now recorded by visiting every home individually. This results in considerable loss of human hours and also provides considerable details regarding the average consumption of a locality so that power supply can be made according to these data. This will help the officials in deciding the specifications of transformers and other instruments required in power transmission.

This idea is economically efficient as well because we can get the meter reading at a very low cost. The implementation is done in such a way that a SMS is delivered to the Modem whose reading is to be noted and then that meter replies to the server in the SMS format and it is known that SMS costs are very low. The purpose of this project is to remote monitoring and control of the Domestic Energy meter. This system enables the Electricity Department to read the meter readings regularly without the person visiting each house. This can be achieved by the use of Microcontroller unit that continuously monitors and records the Energy Meter readings in its permanent (non-volatile) memory location.

This system is made to keep the records about the bills of the customers. The admin can manage all the accounts and the registered users like employees and customers can only manage their own accounts. This system helps in maintaining the bills and the payments. A different

module is there for employees to check the customer's details if their job requires. Admin, employees, and customers all have a different interface and different privileges according to their need. Like a customer can only manage his account and cannot see any details of other customers, employees can see the details of all the customer's accounts and admin can manage all the accounts including the customers and employees account. This system also has the option for customers to pay their electricity bills by online mode. Either through internet banking or by debit card.

This system also has the feature to add and delete customer and employee's accounts in case a customer wants to cut the connection or an employee wants to leave the job. All the employees are divided into different departments according to their job profile and the customers are divided according to their wards. The rest of the modules are explained in the further sections with the detailed explanation.

This application is used to continuously record the readings and the live meter reading can be send to the Electricity department on request. This system also can be used to disconnect the power supply to the house in case of non-payment of electricity bills. Then this system is used to pay the electricity charge through the online payment. Then this system is also used to find calculation of how much of units and amount are used at a particular home appliance at the month usage

EXISTING SYSTEM:

In the presented system all the jobs of the electricity board is prepared by hand, it is very complicated to the operators and needs to keep the objects records of the office and a separate record for the billing and customer details. Many irregularities exist in the present system, which is manually maintained. It requires high processing time.

Errors may also occur in this system. These details are all stored in special records. Though all the most importance, tedious a care needed job is the bill calculation. Any one of mistakes may cause severe consequence. The firm handles all of the work manually, which is very tedious and mismanaged.

DISADVANTAGE:

- That is not user friendly.
- The retrieval and storing of data is slow.
- Data is not maintained efficiently.
- Existing system requires lot of paper work and even a small transaction require many papers fill.

PROPOSED SYSTEM:

This proposed EB Bill Management project overcomes all these drawbacks with the features aforementioned. It is beneficial to both consumers and the electricity board. With the new system, there is reduction in the number of staffs to be employed by the company. The working speed and performance of the software is faster with high performance which saves time. Furthermore, there is very little chance of miscalculation and being corrupted by the staffs.

The proposed system provides managing of huge data effectively and efficiently for efficient results, storing the details of the customers, employees etc. in such a way that the database can be modified. Proposed system supports strategic competitive advantages. Since the proposed systems provide easiness in reports generating it will provide strategic advantages among competitors. Our proposed system is used to monitor the electricity usage of home is monitor easily and also monitor the usage of units and amount at the particular home appliances. Then the amount of electricity usage by that month is previously fixed at admin, then the intimation status has been sent to the user once they reaches the limited level.

ADVANTAGE:

- The proposed system is user friendly.
- The retrieval and storing of data is fast and data is maintained efficiently.

- All the data is fed into the computer immediately and various bills and reports can be generated through computers.
- All the data is kept in a database no data of the organization can be destroyed. Moreover work becomes very easy because there is no need to keep data on papers.
- Computer operator control will be there no errors. Moreover storing and retrieving of information is easy. So work can be done speedily and in time

NON FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Hardware Requirements

- Processor (CPU) : Intel Core i5 or i7
- Memory : 4GB+
- Hard Drive : 100GB+ SSD
- Battery Life : 4+ Hours
- Wireless Network Cards : Required
- USB port : 3
- Sound Card : Yes
- Screen Size : 13+ inch
- RJ45 Cable : 8 ft

Software Requirements

- Operating system : Windows 7/8/10
- Microsoft Office : 2010
- Front End : ASP.Net

- Back End : MSSQL
- Design : HTML/CSS
- System type : 32-bit Operating System
- IDE : Visual Studio 2010

DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

A data-flow diagram is a way of representing a flow of a data of a process or a system. The DFD also provides information about the outputs and inputs of each entity and the process itself. A data-flow diagram has no control flow, there are no decision rules and no loops.

The visual representation makes it a good communication tool between User and System designer. Structure of DFD allows starting from a broad overview and expand it to a hierarchy of detailed diagrams. DFD has often been used due to the following reasons: ... Determination of physical system construction requirements.

Data flow Symbols:

Symbol	Description
	An entity . A source of data or a destination for data.
	A process or task that is performed by the system.
	A data store , a place where data is held between processes.
	A data flow .

DATA FLOW DIAGRAM:

LEVEL 0:

A level 0 data flow diagram (DFD), also known as a context diagram, shows a data system as a whole and emphasizes the way it interacts with external entities. This DFD level 0 example shows how such a system might function within a typical retail business.

LEVEL 1:

A context level DFD is the most basic form of DFD. It aims to show how the entire system works at a glance. There is only one process in the system and all the data flows either into or out of this process. Context level DFD's demonstrates the interactions between the process and external entities.

LEVEL 2:

A level 2 data flow diagram (DFD) offers a more detailed look at the processes that make up an information system than a level 1 DFD does. It can be used to plan or record the specific makeup of a system. ... You can then input the particulars of your own system.

LEVEL 3:

The necessary level of detail depends on the scope of what you are trying to accomplish. Data flow diagrams are used to graphically represent the flow of data in a business information system.

ER-DIAGRAM

An entity–relationship model describes interrelated things of interest in a specific domain of knowledge. A basic ER model is composed of entity types and specifies relationships that can exist between entities.

ER diagrams are used to analyze existing databases to find and resolve problems in logic or deployment. Drawing the diagram should reveal where it's going wrong. Business information systems: The diagrams are used to design or analyze relational databases used in business processes.

ER diagrams are a visual representation of your database. It highlights the entities of your system and the relationship between those entities. You can easily create them using our ER diagram tool. It is useful to document the system and much easier to explain to an external party compared to a database design.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE:

MODULES

- 1. Admin.**
- 2. User Registration and Login.**
- 3. Level of Energy Consumption.**
- 4. Status of User**
- 5. Intimation of Power Consumption**
- 6. Payment**
- 7. Report**

Use Case Description

Admin

The entire process has been maintained by the admin, from which the details and the complete reference for the users has been provided. Admin holds the records and lists of the entire users involved in the system and their power consumption level which provides the detailed structure to the users.

User Registration and Login

The users have to register their necessary details to the administrator to gain the access for the system, from which the customer can get the username and password .After accessing the system the customers can get the complete knowledge about the energy usage level, cost, status intimation that has been provided by the administrator.

Level of Energy Consumption

This module provides the detailed statement of the energy consumption level of the customer which helps to maintain their usage level. Whereas it also increases the efficiency of the entire system by maintaining the records of customers and their consumption level involved in the system.

Status of User

The admin receives and holds the status of each and every customers involved in the process, and gain the access control to manipulate them. This module helps the administrator for further process which enhances to complete system with better efficiency.

Intimation of Power Consumption

This module intimates the consumption level of the customers to them through their mobile, so that the customers can gather their day to day consumption level and usage. The customer receives a message if they crossed their daily usage limit, which helps them to maintain their level of usage.

Payment

The payment can be done through online which reduces paper valuation and manual work. Increases the efficient and a time saving procedure for the customers and as well as the administrator.

Report

The complete procedure has been maintain in this module which enhance the system by providing the list and details of the customers and about their energy usages. It helps the administrator to improve the performance evaluation of the system.

UML Diagram

Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a general purpose modelling language. The main aim of UML is to define a standard way to visualize the way a system has been designed. It is quite similar to blueprints used in other fields of engineering. UML is not a programming language, it is rather a visual language. We use UML diagrams to portray the behavior and structure of a system. UML helps software engineers, businessmen and system architects with modelling, design and analysis. The Object Management Group (OMG) adopted Unified Modelling Language as a standard. Its been managed by OMG ever since. International Organization for Standardization (ISO) published UML. UML has been revised over the years and is reviewed periodically.

The current UML standards call for 13 different types of diagrams: class, activity, object, use case, sequence, package, state, component, communication, composite structure, interaction overview, timing, and deployment.

UML (Unified Modeling Language) is a modeling language used by software developers. UML can be used to develop diagrams and provide users (programmers) with ready-to-use, expressive modeling examples. Some UML tools generate program language code from UML.

UML helps to organize, plan and visualize a program. In addition, being a standard, it is widely used and accepted as the language for outlining programs. UML is used in a variety of purposes and its readability and re-usability make it an ideal choice for programmers.

Use case Diagram

Use Case Diagrams are used to depict the functionality of a system or a part of a system. They are widely used to illustrate the functional requirements of the system and its interaction with external agents(actors). A use case is basically a diagram representing different scenarios where the system can be used. A use case diagram gives us a high level view of what the system or a part of the system does without going into implementation details.

Sequence Diagram

A sequence diagram simply depicts interaction between objects in a sequential order i.e. the order in which these interactions take place. We can also use the terms event diagrams or event scenarios to refer to a sequence diagram. Sequence diagrams describe how and in what order the objects in a system function. These diagrams are widely used by businessmen and software developers to document and understand requirements for new and existing systems.

Collaborative Diagram

Collaboration diagram is another form of interaction diagram. It represents the structural organization of a system and the messages sent/received. Structural organization consists of objects and links.

The purpose of collaboration diagram is similar to sequence diagram. However, the specific purpose of collaboration diagram is to visualize the organization of objects and their interaction.

Class Diagram

The most widely use UML diagram is the class diagram. It is the building block of all object oriented software systems. We use class diagrams to depict the static structure of a system by showing system's classes, their methods and attributes. Class diagrams also help us identify relationship between different classes or objects.

Activity Diagram

We use Activity Diagrams to illustrate the flow of control in a system. We can also use an activity diagram to refer to the steps involved in the execution of a use case. We model sequential and concurrent activities using activity diagrams. So, we basically depict workflows visually using an activity diagram. An activity diagram focuses on condition of flow and the sequence in which it happens. We describe or depict what causes a particular event using an activity diagram.

DESIGN

Admin Login

Smart ElectricityBilling

HOME ADMIN LOGIN USER LOGIN REGISTRATION

ADMIN LOGIN

NAME	<input type="text"/>
PASSWORD	<input type="password"/>
	<input type="button" value="LOGIN"/>

Label

User Login

The screenshot shows the 'User Login' page of the 'Smart Electricity Billing' system. The page has a dark header with the title 'Smart Electricity Billing' in white. Below the header is a blue navigation bar with links for 'HOME', 'ADMIN LOGIN', 'USER LOGIN', and 'REGISTRATION'. The main content area is white and features a 'USER LOGIN' heading. Below the heading is a form with three rows: 'NAME' with a text input field, 'PASSWORD' with a text input field, and a 'LOGIN' button. A 'Label' text is positioned below the form. At the bottom of the page is a blue footer with the text 'COPYRIGHT © ELECTRIC |'.

Smart Electricity Billing	
HOME	ADMIN LOGIN USER LOGIN REGISTRATION
USER LOGIN	
NAME	<input type="text"/>
PASSWORD	<input type="text"/>
	<input type="button" value="LOGIN"/>
	Label
COPYRIGHT © ELECTRIC	

User Register

The screenshot shows the 'User Register' page of the 'Smart Electricity Billing' system. The page has a dark header with the title 'Smart Electricity Billing' in white. Below the header is a blue navigation bar with links for 'HOME', 'ADMIN LOGIN', 'USER LOGIN', and 'REGISTRATION'. The main content area is white and features a 'Register Page' heading. Below the heading is a form with eight rows of input fields: 'Name', 'FatherName', 'EB Number', 'Mobile No', 'EMail Id', 'Address', 'UserName', and 'Password'. A 'Conform Password' label is positioned below the 'Password' field, followed by a 'Conform Password' input field. A 'Submit' button is located at the bottom of the form. A vertical scrollbar is visible on the right side of the page.

Smart Electricity Billing	
HOME	ADMIN LOGIN USER LOGIN REGISTRATION
Register Page	
Name	<input type="text"/>
FatherName	<input type="text"/>
EB Number	<input type="text"/>
Mobile No	<input type="text"/>
EMail Id	<input type="text"/>
Address	<input type="text"/>
UserName	<input type="text"/>
Password	<input type="text"/>
Conform Password	<input type="text"/>
	<input type="button" value="Submit"/>

Unit Fixed

Smart ElectricityBilling

FIXED UNIT METER BOX ELECTRICITY BILL USAGE REQUEST USER REVIEW

FIX UNIT FOR THIS MONTH

Owner Name	<input type="text"/>
UNIT	<input type="text"/>
PHONE NUMBER	<input type="text"/>
	<input type="button" value="ALERT"/>

Label

COPYRIGHT © ELECTRIC |

Meter Box

READING AREA

Fan			
Fridge			
AC			
TV			

TV

Mixie

Unit Usage

FAN	FRIDGE	AC	TV	MIXIE
<input type="text" value="165"/>	<input type="text" value="40"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>

165

BILL PAYMENT

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Payment

PAYMENT METHOD DETAILS

PAYMENT DATE	1-20-2020
EB NUMBER	<input type="text"/>
NAME	<input type="text"/>
MOBILE NO	<input type="text"/>
UNIT	280
AMOUNT	1400
CARD TYPE	select ▾
CARD NO	<input type="text"/>
CVV	<input type="text"/>
EXP DATE	<input type="text"/> <small>...</small>
	<input type="button" value="PAY"/>
Label	

COPYRIGHT © ELECTRIC |

Usage Request

The screenshot shows the 'Usage Request' form within the 'Smart ElectricityBilling' application. The header is dark grey with the logo 'Smart ElectricityBilling' in white and blue. A blue navigation bar contains five menu items: 'FIXED UNIT', 'METER BOX', 'ELECTRICITY BILL', 'USAGE REQUEST', and 'USER REVIEW'. The main content area has a light blue background and a white form box. The form title is 'GET YOUR ELECTRICITY USAGE REPORT FOR THIS MONTH'. It contains three rows: the first row has a label 'NAME' and a text input field with 'taju'; the second row has a label 'EB NUMBER' and a text input field with '70001'; the third row has a 'GET REPORT' button. A 'Label' text is centered below the form.

NAME	taju
EB NUMBER	70001
<input type="button" value="GET REPORT"/>	

Label

User Feedback

The screenshot shows the 'User Feedback' form within the 'Smart ElectricityBilling' application. The header and navigation bar are identical to the 'Usage Request' form. The main content area has a light blue background and a white form box. The form title is 'TELL YOUR EXPERIENCE ABOUT OUR SERVICE'. It contains three rows: the first row has a label 'NAME' and a text input field with 'taju'; the second row has a label 'FEEDBACK' and a text input field; the third row has a 'REVIEW' button. A 'Label' text is centered below the form.

NAME	taju
FEEDBACK	
<input type="button" value="REVIEW"/>	

Label

User Approval

Smart ElectricityBilling

USER APPROVAL VIEW USERS VIEW PAYMENT VIEW REPORTS LOGOUT

VIEW USER DETAILS

New User

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View Users

Smart ElectricityBilling

USER APPROVAL VIEW USERS VIEW PAYMENT VIEW REPORTS LOGOUT

VIEW USERS

Name	FatherName	EbNumber	MobileNo	EmailID	Address	Username	Password	Status
Tajudeen	shabu	17001	9790530960	taj@gmail.com	28 120 kers woralyur	taju	123	Approved

Payment List

Smart ElectricityBilling

USER APPROVAL VIEW USERS VIEW PAYMENT VIEW REPORTS LOGOUT

VIEW PAYMENT

Payment_Date	EB_number	Name	Phone	Unit	Amount	CardType	CardNo	Cvv	ExpiryDate
12-24-2019	17001	taju	9790530960	26	130	MASTER CARD	11111111111111111111	435	29-11-2019

View Reports

Smart ElectricityBilling

USER APPROVAL VIEW USERS VIEW PAYMENT VIEW REPORTS LOGOUT

VIEW REPORTS

Id	Name	Feedback
1	taju	Its Good For Reduce Our Bill

SAMPLE CODING

Admin Login.aspx

```
<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="AdminLogin.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ElectricityBill.AdminLogin" %>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
```

```
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head runat="server">
  <title>Electric Vehicle</title>
  <meta name="description" content="website description" />
  <meta name="keywords" content="website keywords, website keywords" />
  <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" />
  <link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="style/style.css" title="style" />
  <style type="text/css">
    .style1
    {
      width: 97%;
      height: 211px;
    }
  </style>
</head>
<body>
  <div id="main">
    <div id="header">
      <div id="logo">
        <div id="logo_text">
          <!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->
          <h1><a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>
          <h2></h2>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
    <div id="menubar">
      <ul id="menu">
        <!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're
on -->
        <li class="selected"><a href="index.html">Home</a></li>
        <li><a href="AdminLogin.aspx">Admin Login</a></li>
        <li><a href="UserLogin.aspx">User Login</a></li>
        <li><a href="Registration.aspx">Registration</a></li>
      </ul>
```

```

</div>
</div>
<div id="site_content">

  <div id="content">

<form id="form1" runat="server">
<div>

  <br />
  <br />
  <asp:Label ID="Label1" runat="server" Font-Bold="True" Font-Size="X-Large"
    ForeColor="#0066FF" Text="ADMIN LOGIN"></asp:Label>
  <br />
  <br />
  <table align="center" class="style1">
    <tr>
      <td>
        <asp:Label ID="Label2" runat="server" Text="NAME"></asp:Label>
      </td>
      <td>
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox1" runat="server" Height="30px"
Width="140px"></asp:TextBox>
      </td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
      <td>
        <asp:Label ID="Label3" runat="server" Text="PASSWORD"></asp:Label>
      </td>
      <td>
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox2" runat="server" Height="30px" Width="140px"
        TextMode="Password"></asp:TextBox>
      </td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
      <td>
        &nbsp;</td>
      <td>
        <asp:Button ID="Button1" runat="server" Height="34px" onclick="Button1_Click"
        Text="LOGIN" Width="82px" />
      </td>
    </tr>
  </table>
  <asp:Label ID="Label4" runat="server" Text="Label"></asp:Label>
  <br />
  <br />

```

```
<br />
</div>
</form>
</div>
</div>
<div id="footer">
  Copyright &copy; Electric |
</div>
</div>
</body>
</html>
```

Admin Login.aspx.cs

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;

namespace ElectricityBill
{
    public partial class AdminLogin : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {

        }

        protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {

        }
    }
}
```

```

string a, b, c, d;
a = "admin";
b = "admin";
c = TextBox1.Text;
d = TextBox2.Text;
if (a == c && b == d)
{
    Response.Redirect("UserApproval.aspx");
}
else
{
    Label4.Text = "username or password mismatched";
}
}
}
}

```

Fixed Unit.aspx

```

<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="FixedUnit.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ElectricityBill.FixedUnit" %>

```

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
    <title>Smart Electricity</title>
    <meta name="description" content="website description" />
    <meta name="keywords" content="website keywords, website keywords" />
    <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" />
    <link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="style/style.css" title="style" />
    <style type="text/css">
        .style1
        {
            width: 97%;
            height: 211px;
        }
    </style>
</head>
<body>
<div id="main">
    <div id="header">
        <div id="logo">
            <div id="logo_text">
                <!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->

```

```

    <h1><a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>
    <h2></h2>
</div>
</div>
<div id="menubar">
    <ul id="menu">
        <!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're
on -->
        <li class="selected"><a href="FixedUnit.aspx">Fixed Unit</a></li>
        <li><a href="UnitCalculation.aspx">Meter Box</a></li>
        <li><a href="PayBill.aspx">Electricity Bill</a></li>
        <li><a href="UsageRequest.aspx">Usage Request</a></li>
        <li><a href="UserReview.aspx">User Review</a></li>
        <li><a href="UserLogin.aspx">Logout</a></li>
    </ul>
</div>
</div>
<div id="site_content">

    <div id="content">

<form id="form1" runat="server">
<div>

    <br />
    <br />
    <asp:Label ID="Label1" runat="server" Font-Bold="True" Font-Size="X-Large"
    ForeColor="#0066FF" Text="FIX UNIT FOR THIS MONTH"></asp:Label>
    <br />

    <table align="center" class="style1">
        <tr>
            <td>
                <asp:Label ID="Label5" runat="server" Text="Owner Name"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox3" runat="server" Height="30px"
Width="140px"></asp:TextBox>
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <td>
                <asp:Label ID="Label2" runat="server" Text="UNIT"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>

```

```

        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox1" runat="server" Height="30px"
Width="140px"></asp:TextBox>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>
    <asp:Label ID="Label3" runat="server" Text="PHONE NUMBER"></asp:Label>
</td>
<td>
    <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox2" runat="server" Height="30px"
Width="140px"></asp:TextBox>
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>
    &nbsp;</td>
<td>
    <asp:Button ID="Button1" runat="server" Height="34px" onclick="Button1_Click"
Text="ALERT" Width="82px" />
</td>
</tr>
</table>
<asp:Label ID="Label4" runat="server" Text="Label"></asp:Label>
<br />

</div>
</form>
</div>
</div>
<div id="footer">
    Copyright &copy; Electric |
</div>
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

Fixed Unit.aspx.cs

```

using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;

```

```

namespace ElectricityBill
{
    public partial class FixedUnit : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {

        }

        protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            Session["unit"] = TextBox1.Text;
            Session["mob"] = TextBox2.Text;
            Session["name"] = TextBox1.Text;
            Response.Redirect("UnitCalculation.aspx");
        }
    }
}

```

PayBill.aspx

```

<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="PayBill.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ElectricityBill.PayBill" %>

```

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">

```

```

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head runat="server">
    <title></title>
    <style type="text/css">

```

```

*
{ margin: 0 0 8px 0;
padding: 0;
text-align: center;
}

```

```

#logo_text h1, #logo_text h1 a, #logo_text h1 a:hover
{ padding: 22px 0 0 0;
color: #FFF;
letter-spacing: 0.1em;
text-decoration: none;}

```

```

#logo h1, #logo h2

```

```
{ font: normal 300% 'century gothic', arial, sans-serif;
border-bottom: 0;
text-transform: none;
margin: 0;}
```

```
h1, h2, h3, h4, h5, h6
{ font: normal 175% 'century gothic', arial, sans-serif;
color: #43423F;
margin: 0 0 15px 0;
padding: 15px 0 5px 0;}
```

```
a, a:hover
{ outline: none;
text-decoration: underline;
color: #FD5BFF;}
```

```
#logo_text h1 a .logo_colour
{ color: #1293EE;}
```

```
#logo_text h2
{ font-size: 100%;
padding: 4px 0 0 0;
color: #DDD;}
```

```
h2
{ font: normal 175% 'century gothic', arial, sans-serif;
color: #1293EE;}
```

```
ul#menu, ul#menu li
{ float: left;
margin: 0;
padding: 0;}
```

```
ul
{ margin: 2px 0 22px 17px;}
```

```
ul#menu li
{ list-style: none;}
```

```
ul li
{ list-style-type: circle;
margin: 0 0 6px 0;
padding: 0 0 4px 5px;}
```

```
ul#menu li a:hover, ul#menu li.selected a, ul#menu li.selected a:hover
{ color: #FFF;}
```

```

background: #0D66A5;}

ul#menu li a
{ letter-spacing: 0.1em;
font: normal 100% arial, sans-serif;
display: block;
float: left;
height: 37px;
padding: 29px 26px 6px 26px;
text-align: center;
color: #FFF;
text-transform: uppercase;
text-decoration: none;
background: transparent;}

table
{ margin: 10px 0 30px 1px;
width: 826px;
}

table tr td
{ background: #F0EFE2;
color: #47433F;
border-top: 1px solid #FFF;}

table tr th, table tr td
{ background: #3B3B3B;
color: #FFF;
padding: 7px 4px;
text-align: center;
}

</style>
</head>
<body>
<form id="form1" runat="server">
<div>

<title>Smart Electricity</title>
<meta content="website description" name="description" />
<meta content="website keywords, website keywords" name="keywords" />
<meta content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" http-equiv="content-type" />
<link href="style/style.css" rel="stylesheet" title="style" type="text/css" />
<style type="text/css">

```

```

tbody{background:transparent;border:0 none;font-
size:100%;margin:0;padding:0;border:0;outline:0;vertical-align:top;}
tr{background:transparent;border:0 none;font-
size:100%;margin:0;padding:0;border:0;outline:0;vertical-align:top;}
table td:first-child {font-weight:bold;}

table td { padding:9px 10px 8px 20px;
text-align: left;
}
table td {padding:0;border:none;border-collapse:collapse;}
.style2
{
width: 287px;
}
.style4
{
height: 35px;
}
.style5
{
height: 35px;
}
.style6
{
width: 287px;
height: 40px;
}
.style7
{
height: 40px;
}
</style>
<div id="main">
<div id="header">
<div id="logo">
<div id="logo_text">
<!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->
<h1>
<a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>
<h2>
</h2>
</div>
</div>
<div id="menubar">
<ul id="menu">

```

<!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're on -->

```
<li class="selected"><a href="FixedUnit.aspx">Fixed Unit</a></li>
<li><a href="UnitCalculation.aspx">Meter Box</a></li>
<li><a href="PayBill.aspx">Electricity Bill</a></li>
<li><a href="UsageRequest.aspx">Usage Request</a></li>
<li><a href="UserReview.aspx">User Review</a></li>
<li><a href="UserLogin.aspx">Logout</a></li>
</ul>
</div>
</div>
<div id="site_content">
<div id="content">
```

```
<table>
<tr>
<td class="style4" colspan="2">
<asp:Label ID="Label3" runat="server" Font-Size="Large"
ForeColor="#990000"
Text="PAYMENT METHOD DETAILS"></asp:Label>
</td>
<td class="style5">
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td colspan="2" class="style4">
</td>
<td class="style4">
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td class="style2">
<asp:Label ID="Label14" runat="server" Font-Size="Small"
ForeColor="#990000"
Text="PAYMENT DATE"></asp:Label>
</td>
<td>
<asp:Label ID="Label15" runat="server" Font-Size="Large"
ForeColor="#FF3399"></asp:Label>
</td>
<td>
&nbsp;</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td class="style2">
```

```

                <asp:Label ID="Label12" runat="server" Font-Size="Small"
ForeColor="#990000"
                Text="EB NUMBER"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox6" runat="server" BorderWidth="1px"
Height="21px"></asp:TextBox>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:RequiredFieldValidator ID="RequiredFieldValidator4" runat="server"
ControlToValidate="TextBox6" Display="Dynamic"
ErrorMessage="*Please Enter"
                ForeColor="#FF3300"></asp:RequiredFieldValidator>
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <td class="style2">
                <asp:Label ID="Label4" runat="server" Font-Size="Small"
ForeColor="#990000"
                Text="NAME"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox1" runat="server" BorderWidth="1px"
Height="21px"></asp:TextBox>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:RequiredFieldValidator ID="RequiredFieldValidator1" runat="server"
ControlToValidate="TextBox1" Display="Dynamic"
ErrorMessage="*Please Enter"
                ForeColor="#FF3300"></asp:RequiredFieldValidator>
                &nbsp;</td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <td class="style2">
                <asp:Label ID="Label9" runat="server" Font-Size="Small"
ForeColor="#990000"
                Text="MOBILE NO"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox2" runat="server" BorderWidth="1px"
Height="21px"></asp:TextBox>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:RegularExpressionValidator ID="RegularExpressionValidator1"
runat="server"
                ControlToValidate="TextBox2" Display="Dynamic"

```

```

                ErrorMessage="*enter Valid Mobile no" ForeColor="#FF3300"
                ValidationExpression="[0-9]{10}"></asp:RegularExpressionValidator>
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <td class="style2">
                <asp:Label ID="Label13" runat="server" Font-Size="Small"
                ForeColor="#990000"
                Text="UNIT"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox7" runat="server" BorderWidth="1px" Font-
                Size="X-Large"
                ForeColor="Lime" Height="26px" ReadOnly="True"
                Width="47px"></asp:TextBox>
            </td>
            <td>
                &nbsp;   </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <td class="style6">
                <asp:Label ID="Label10" runat="server" Font-Size="Small"
                ForeColor="#990000"
                Text="AMOUNT"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td class="style7">
                <asp:Label ID="Label11" runat="server" Font-Size="Large"
                ForeColor="#009900"
                Text="Rs.5000"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td class="style7">
                &nbsp;   </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <td class="style2">
                <asp:Label ID="Label5" runat="server" Font-Size="Small"
                ForeColor="#990000"
                Text="CARD TYPE"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:DropDownList ID="DropDownList1" runat="server" Height="22px">
                    <asp:ListItem>select</asp:ListItem>
                    <asp:ListItem>VISA CARD</asp:ListItem>
                    <asp:ListItem>MASTER CARD</asp:ListItem>
                </asp:DropDownList>
            </td>
        </tr>
    </tbody>
</table>

```

```

        <td>
            &nbsp;</td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td class="style2">
            <asp:Label ID="Label6" runat="server" Font-Size="Small"
ForeColor="#990000"
            Text="CARD NO"></asp:Label>
        </td>
        <td>
            <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox3" runat="server" BorderWidth="1px"
Height="21px"
            Width="124px"></asp:TextBox>
        </td>
        <td>
            <asp:RegularExpressionValidator ID="RegularExpressionValidator2"
runat="server"
            ControlToValidate="TextBox3" Display="Dynamic"
            ErrorMessage="*enter Valid Card No" ForeColor="#FF3300"
            ValidationExpression="[0-9]{16}"></asp:RegularExpressionValidator>
        </td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td class="style2">
            <asp:Label ID="Label7" runat="server" Font-Size="Small"
ForeColor="#990000"
            Text="CVV"></asp:Label>
        </td>
        <td>
            &nbsp;<asp:TextBox ID="TextBox4" runat="server" BorderWidth="1px"
Height="21px"></asp:TextBox>
        </td>
        <td>
            <asp:RequiredFieldValidator ID="RequiredFieldValidator3" runat="server"
            ControlToValidate="TextBox4" Display="Dynamic"
            ErrorMessage="*Please Enter"
            ForeColor="#FF3300"></asp:RequiredFieldValidator>
        </td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td class="style2">
            <asp:Label ID="Label8" runat="server" Font-Size="Small"
ForeColor="#990000"
            Text="EXP DATE"></asp:Label>
        </td>
        <td>

```


PayBill.aspx.cs

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Data.SqlClient;
using System.Configuration;
using System.Net;
using System.IO;

namespace ElectricityBill
{
    public partial class PayBill : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection(ConfigurationManager.ConnectionStrings["db"].ToString());
        protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            TextBox7.Text = Session["name"].ToString();
            int unit = int.Parse(TextBox7.Text);
            int tot = unit * 5;
            Label11.Text = tot.ToString();
            Calendar1.Visible = false;
            Label15.Text=DateTime.Now.ToString("M/d/yyyy");
        }

        protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            string a;
            a = "Hi Your Payment has been Send and Successfully Debited amount is: " +
Label11.Text + " And Totally Your Usage In This Month "+TextBox7.Text+" Units Thanks
Visit Again";

            con.Open();
            SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("insert into Payment
values("+Label15.Text+", "+TextBox6.Text+", "+ TextBox1.Text + ", "+ TextBox2.Text +
", "+TextBox7.Text+", "+ Label11.Text + ", "+ DropDownList1.SelectedValue + ", "+
TextBox3.Text + ", "+ TextBox4.Text + ", "+ TextBox5.Text + ")", con);
            cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
            con.Close();
            Response.Write("<script>alert('Transaction Successfully ')</script>");
            sendmessage(TextBox2.Text, a);
        }
    }
}
```

```

    }
    public void sendmessage(string targetno, string message)
    {

        // use the API URL here
        String query = "http://pay4sms.in/sendsms/?token=
b81edee36bcef4ddbbaa6ef535f8db03e&credit=2&sender=
RandDC&message=testsms&number=919150028012=" + targetno + "&message=" + message;

        //string query = "
http://bulksms.mysmsmantra.com:8080/WebSMS/SMSAPI.jsp?username=OculusTech&passwo
rd=1526762373&sendername=OCULUS&mobilen=" + targetno + "&message=" + message;
        WebClient client = new WebClient();
        Stream sin = client.OpenRead(query);
        Response.Write("<script language=javascript>alert('successfully Message
Send')</script>");
    }
    protected void Button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        Calendar1.Visible = true;
    }

    protected void Calendar1_SelectionChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        TextBox5.Text = Calendar1.SelectedDate.ToShortDateString();
    }
}
}

```

User Registration.aspx

```

<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="Registration.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ElectricityBill.Register" %>

```

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">

```

```

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head runat="server">
    <title>Smart Electricity Bill</title>
    <meta name="description" content="website description" />
    <meta name="keywords" content="website keywords, website keywords" />
    <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" />
    <link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="style/style.css" title="style" />
    <style type="text/css">

```

```
tbody{background:transparent;border:0 none;font-
size:100%;margin:0;padding:0;border:0;outline:0;vertical-align:top;}
tr{background:transparent;border:0 none;font-
size:100%;margin:0;padding:0;border:0;outline:0;vertical-align:top;}
table td:first-child {font-weight:bold;}

table td { padding:9px 10px 8px 20px;
text-align: left;
}
table td {padding:0;border:none;border-collapse:collapse;}</style>
</head>
<body>
<div id="main">
<div id="header">
<div id="logo">
<div id="logo_text">
<!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->
<h1><a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>
<h2></h2>
</div>
</div>
<div id="menubar">
<ul id="menu">
<!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're
on -->
<li class="selected"><a href="index.html">Home</a></li>
<li><a href="AdminLogin.aspx">Admin Login</a></li>
<li><a href="UserLogin.aspx">User Login</a></li>
<li><a href="Registration.aspx">Registration</a></li>

</ul>
</div>
</div>
<div id="site_content">

<div id="content">

<form id="form1" runat="server">
<div>

<table class="style1">
<tr>
<td class="style3" style="width: 322px">
&nbsp;   </td>
```

```

        <td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
            &nbsp;</td>
        <td style="width: 467px">
            &nbsp;</td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td class="style3" style="width: 322px">
            &nbsp;</td>
        <td colspan="2">
            <asp:Label ID="Label1" runat="server" Font-Size="Large" ForeColor="#CC3300"
                Text="Register Page"></asp:Label>
        </td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td class="style3" style="width: 322px">
            &nbsp;</td>
        <td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
            &nbsp;</td>
        <td style="width: 467px">
            &nbsp;</td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td class="style3" rowspan="8" style="width: 322px">
            <asp:Image ID="Image1" runat="server" Height="369px"
                ImageUrl="~/images/signup.jpeg" Visible="False" Width="206px" />
        </td>
        <td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
            <asp:Label ID="Label2" runat="server" Text="Name"></asp:Label>
        </td>
        <td style="width: 467px">
            <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox1" runat="server" BackColor="#999966"
                BorderColor="Black" ForeColor="Black" Height="28px"
Width="146px"></asp:TextBox>
            <asp:RequiredFieldValidator ID="RequiredFieldValidator2" runat="server"
                ControlToValidate="TextBox1" Display="Dynamic" ErrorMessage="*Please
Enter "
                ForeColor="#FF3300"></asp:RequiredFieldValidator>
        </td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td class="style2" style="height: 40px; width: 99px">
            <asp:Label ID="Label3" runat="server" Text="FatherName"></asp:Label>
        </td>
        <td style="height: 40px; width: 467px;">
            <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox2" runat="server" BackColor="#999966"

```

```

        BorderColor="Black" ForeColor="Black" Height="28px"
Width="146px"></asp:TextBox>
        <asp:RequiredFieldValidator ID="RequiredFieldValidator1" runat="server"
ControlToValidate="TextBox2" Display="Dynamic" ErrorMessage="*Please
Enter"
        ForeColor="#FF3300"></asp:RequiredFieldValidator>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
        <asp:Label ID="Label4" runat="server" Text="EB Number"></asp:Label>
    </td>
<td>
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox11" runat="server" BackColor="#999966"
        BorderColor="Black" ForeColor="Black" Height="28px"
Width="146px"></asp:TextBox>
        <asp:RequiredFieldValidator ID="RequiredFieldValidator9" runat="server"
ControlToValidate="TextBox11" Display="Dynamic" ErrorMessage="*Please
Enter"
        ForeColor="#FF3300"></asp:RequiredFieldValidator>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
        <asp:Label ID="Label7" runat="server" Text="Mobile No"></asp:Label>
    </td>
<td style="width: 467px">
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox5" runat="server" BackColor="#999966"
        BorderColor="Black" ForeColor="Black" Height="28px"
Width="146px"></asp:TextBox>
        <asp:RegularExpressionValidator ID="RegularExpressionValidator1"
runat="server"
ControlToValidate="TextBox5" Display="Dynamic"
ErrorMessage="Enter Valid Mobile No " ForeColor="#990000"
ValidationExpression="[0-9]{10}"></asp:RegularExpressionValidator>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
        <asp:Label ID="Label8" runat="server" Text="EMail Id"></asp:Label>
    </td>
<td style="width: 467px">
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox6" runat="server" BackColor="#999966"
        BorderColor="Black" ForeColor="Black" Height="28px"
Width="146px"></asp:TextBox>
        <asp:RequiredFieldValidator ID="RequiredFieldValidator7" runat="server"

```

```

ControlToValidate="TextBox6" Display="Dynamic" ErrorMessage="*Please
Enter"
ForeColor="#FF3300"></asp:RequiredFieldValidator>
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
<asp:Label ID="Label9" runat="server" Text="Address"></asp:Label>
</td>
<td style="width: 467px">
<asp:TextBox ID="TextBox7" runat="server" BackColor="#999966"
Border="Black" ForeColor="Black" Height="28px"
Width="146px"></asp:TextBox>
<asp:RequiredFieldValidator ID="RequiredFieldValidator4" runat="server"
ControlToValidate="TextBox7" Display="Dynamic" ErrorMessage="*Please
Enter"
ForeColor="#FF3300"></asp:RequiredFieldValidator>
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
<asp:Label ID="Label10" runat="server" Text="UserName"></asp:Label>
</td>
<td style="width: 467px">
<asp:TextBox ID="TextBox8" runat="server" BackColor="#999966"
Border="Black" ForeColor="Black" Height="28px"
Width="146px"></asp:TextBox>
<asp:RequiredFieldValidator ID="RequiredFieldValidator6" runat="server"
ControlToValidate="TextBox8" Display="Dynamic" ErrorMessage="*Please
Enter"
ForeColor="#FF3300"></asp:RequiredFieldValidator>
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
<asp:Label ID="Label11" runat="server" Text="Password"></asp:Label>
</td>
<td style="width: 467px">
<asp:TextBox ID="TextBox9" runat="server" BackColor="#999966"
Border="Black" ForeColor="Black" Height="28px" TextMode="Password"
Width="146px"></asp:TextBox>
<asp:RequiredFieldValidator ID="RequiredFieldValidator5" runat="server"
ControlToValidate="TextBox9" Display="Dynamic" ErrorMessage="*Please
Enter"
ForeColor="#FF3300"></asp:RequiredFieldValidator>
</td>

```

```

</tr>
<tr>
  <td class="style3" style="width: 322px">
    &nbsp;  </td>
  <td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
    <asp:Label ID="Label13" runat="server" Text="Conform Password"></asp:Label>
  </td>
  <td style="width: 467px">
&nbsp;  <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox10" runat="server" BackColor="#999966"
BorderColor="Black"
    ForeColor="Black" Height="28px" TextMode="Password"
Width="146px"></asp:TextBox>
    <asp:CompareValidator ID="CompareValidator2" runat="server"
    ControlToCompare="TextBox9" ControlToValidate="TextBox10"
Display="Dynamic"
    ErrorMessage="Enter Correct Password"
ForeColor="#FF3300"></asp:CompareValidator>
  </td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td class="style3" style="width: 322px">
    &nbsp;  </td>
  <td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
    &nbsp;  </td>
  <td style="width: 467px">
    <asp:Button ID="Button1" runat="server" BackColor="Gray" Height="29px"
    onclick="Button1_Click" Text="Submit" Width="79px" />
  </td>
</tr>
<tr>
  <td class="style3" style="width: 322px">
    &nbsp;  </td>
  <td class="style2" style="width: 99px">
    &nbsp;  </td>
  <td style="width: 467px">
    <asp:Label ID="Label12" runat="server"></asp:Label>
  </td>
</tr>
</table>

<br />
<br />

</div>
</form>

```

```

    </div>
</div>
<div id="footer">
    Copyright &copy; Electric |
</div>
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

User Registration.aspx.cs

```

using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Data.SqlClient;
using System.Configuration;

namespace ElectricityBill
{
    public partial class Register : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection(ConfigurationManager.ConnectionStrings["db"].ToString());
        protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {

        }

        protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {

            con.Open();
            SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("insert into register values('" + TextBox1.Text +
"', '" + TextBox2.Text + "', '" + TextBox11.Text + "', '" + TextBox5.Text + "', '" + TextBox6.Text +
"', '" + TextBox7.Text + "', '" + TextBox8.Text + "', '" + TextBox9.Text + "', 'NotApproved')", con);
            cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
            con.Close();
            Response.Write("<script>alert('Your Request sent to Admin....Please wait for Your
Approval ')</script>");
        }
    }
}

```

Unit Calculation.aspx

```
<% @ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="UnitCalculation.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ElectricityBill.UnitCalculation" %>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
```

```
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head runat="server">
  <title></title>
  <style type="text/css">
```

```

    *
    { margin: 0;
      padding: 0;
      text-align: center;
    }

#logo_text h1, #logo_text h1 a, #logo_text h1 a:hover
{ padding: 22px 0 0 0;
  color: #FFF;
  letter-spacing: 0.1em;
  text-decoration: none;}

#logo h1, #logo h2
{ font: normal 300% 'century gothic', arial, sans-serif;
  border-bottom: 0;
  text-transform: none;
  margin: 0;}

h1, h2, h3, h4, h5, h6
{ font: normal 175% 'century gothic', arial, sans-serif;
  color: #43423F;
  margin: 0 0 15px 0;
  padding: 15px 0 5px 0;}

a, a:hover
{ outline: none;
  text-decoration: underline;
  color: #FD5BFF;}

#logo_text h1 a .logo_colour
{ color: #1293EE;}
```

```
#logo_text h2
{ font-size: 100%;
  padding: 4px 0 0 0;
  color: #DDD;}
```

```
h2
{ font: normal 175% 'century gothic', arial, sans-serif;
  color: #1293EE;}
```

```
ul#menu, ul#menu li
{ float: left;
  margin: 0;
  padding: 0;}
```

```
ul
{ margin: 2px 0 22px 17px;}
```

```
ul#menu li
{ list-style: none;}
```

```
ul li
{ list-style-type: circle;
  margin: 0 0 6px 0;
  padding: 0 0 4px 5px;}
```

```
ul#menu li a:hover, ul#menu li.selected a, ul#menu li.selected a:hover
{ color: #FFF;
  background: #0D66A5;}
```

```
ul#menu li a
{ letter-spacing: 0.1em;
  font: normal 100% arial, sans-serif;
  display: block;
  float: left;
  height: 37px;
  padding: 29px 26px 6px 26px;
  text-align: center;
  color: #FFF;
  text-transform: uppercase;
  text-decoration: none;
  background: transparent;}
```

```
table
{ margin: 10px 0 30px 0;
  width: 826px;}
```

```

}

table tr td
{ background: #F0EFE2;
  color: #47433F;
  border-top: 1px solid #FFF;}

table tr th, table tr td
{ background: #3B3B3B;
  color: #FFF;
  padding: 7px 4px;
  text-align: center;
}

.style1
{
  width: 100%;
  border-style: solid;
  border-width: 1px;
}

.style2
{
  width: 100%;
}

</style>
</head>
<body>
  <form id="form1" runat="server">
    <div>

      <title>Smart Electricity Bill </title>
      <meta content="website description" name="description" />
      <meta content="website keywords, website keywords" name="keywords" />
      <meta content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" http-equiv="content-type" />
      <link href="style/style.css" rel="stylesheet" title="style" type="text/css" />
      <div id="main">
        <div id="header">
          <div id="logo">
            <div id="logo_text">
              <!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->
              <h1>
                <a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>
              <h2>

```

```

        </h2>
    </div>
</div>
<div id="menubar">
    <ul id="menu">
        <!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're
on -->
        <li class="selected"><a href="FixedUnit.aspx">Fixed Unit</a></li>
<li><a href="UnitCalculation.aspx">Meter Box</a></li>
<li><a href="PayBill.aspx">Electricity Bill</a></li>
        <li><a href="UsageRequest.aspx">Usage Request</a></li>
<li><a href="UserReview.aspx">User Review</a></li>
<li><a href="UserLogin.aspx">Logout</a></li>
    </ul>
</div>
</div>
<div id="site_content">
    <div id="content">
        <div>
            <br />
            <br />
            <asp:Label ID="Label1" runat="server" Font-Bold="True" Font-Size="X-Large"
                ForeColor="#0066FF" Text="READING AREA"></asp:Label>
            <br />
            <br />
            <table class="style1">
                <tr>
                    <td>
                        <asp:Label ID="Label4" runat="server" Text="Fan" Font-Size="X-
Large"></asp:Label>
                    </td>
                    <td>
                        <asp:Image ID="Image1" runat="server" Height="150px" Width="300px"
                            ImageUrl="~/electronics/2.png" />
                    </td>
                    <td>
                        <asp:ImageButton ID="ImageButton1" runat="server" Height="75px"
                            ImageUrl="~/electronics/6.jpg" onclick="ImageButton1_Click"
Width="75px" />
                    </td>
                    <td>
                        <asp:ImageButton ID="ImageButton6" runat="server" Height="75px"
                            ImageUrl="~/electronics/off.png" onclick="ImageButton6_Click1"
Width="75px" />
                    </td>
                </tr>
            </table>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

```

```

        <tr>
            <td>
                <asp:Label ID="Label5" runat="server" Text="Fridge" Font-Size="X-
Large"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:Image ID="Image2" runat="server" Height="150px" Width="300px"
                ImageUrl="~/electronics/1.jpg" />
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:ImageButton ID="ImageButton2" runat="server" Height="75px"
                ImageUrl="~/electronics/6.jpg" onclick="ImageButton2_Click"
                Width="75px" />
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:ImageButton ID="ImageButton7" runat="server" Height="75px"
                ImageUrl="~/electronics/off.png" onclick="ImageButton7_Click"
                Width="75px" />
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <td>
                <asp:Label ID="Label6" runat="server" Text="AC" Font-Size="X-
Large"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:Image ID="Image3" runat="server" Height="150px" Width="300px"
                ImageUrl="~/electronics/31.jpeg" />
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:ImageButton ID="ImageButton3" runat="server" Height="75px"
                ImageUrl="~/electronics/6.jpg" onclick="ImageButton3_Click"
                Width="75px" />
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:ImageButton ID="ImageButton8" runat="server"
                ImageUrl="~/electronics/off.png" onclick="ImageButton8_Click"
                Width="75px" />
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <td>
                <asp:Label ID="Label7" runat="server" Text="TV" Font-Size="X-
Large"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>

```



```

        <br />
        <asp:ScriptManager ID="sm1" runat="server" />
<asp:UpdatePanel ID="up1" runat="server" UpdateMode="always">
  <ContentTemplate>
    <table class="style2">
      <tr>
        <td>
          <asp:Label ID="Label3" runat="server" Text="FAN"></asp:Label>
          &nbsp;</td>
        <td>
          <asp:Label ID="Label9" runat="server" Text="FRIDGE"></asp:Label>
          &nbsp;</td>
        <td>
          <asp:Label ID="Label10" runat="server" Text="AC"></asp:Label>
          &nbsp;</td>
        <td>
          <asp:Label ID="Label11" runat="server" Text="TV"></asp:Label>
          &nbsp;</td>
        <td>
          <asp:Label ID="Label12" runat="server" Text="MIXIE"></asp:Label>
          &nbsp;</td>
      </tr>
      <tr>
        <td>
          <asp:Timer ID="Timer1" runat="server" Interval="1000"
ontick="Timer1_Tick">
          </asp:Timer>
          <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox5" runat="server" Text="0"></asp:TextBox>
          &nbsp;</td>
        <td>
          <asp:Timer ID="Timer2" runat="server" Interval="1000"
ontick="Timer2_Tick">
          </asp:Timer>
          <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox6" runat="server" Text="0"></asp:TextBox>
          &nbsp;</td>
        <td>
          <asp:Timer ID="Timer3" runat="server" Interval="1000"
ontick="Timer3_Tick">
          </asp:Timer>
          <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox7" runat="server" Text="0"></asp:TextBox>
          &nbsp;</td>
        <td>
          <asp:Timer ID="Timer4" runat="server" Interval="1000"
ontick="Timer4_Tick">
          </asp:Timer>
          <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox8" runat="server" Text="0"></asp:TextBox>

```

```

                &nbsp;</td>
            <td>
                <asp:Timer ID="Timer5" runat="server" Interval="1000"
ontick="Timer5_Tick">
                </asp:Timer>
                <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox9" runat="server" Text="0"></asp:TextBox>
                &nbsp;</td>
            </tr>
        </table>
    </ContentTemplate>
</asp:UpdatePanel>&nbsp;<br />
    <br />
    <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox1" runat="server" Font-Size="XX-Large"
ForeColor="Red"
        Height="42px" ReadOnly="True" Width="60px"></asp:TextBox>
&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<br />
    <br />
    <asp:Button ID="Button1" runat="server" Font-Size="X-Large"
        onclick="Button1_Click" Text="BILL PAYMENT" />
    <br />
    <br />
</div>
</div>
</div>
<div id="footer">
    Copyright © Electric |
    </div>

</div>
</form>
</body>
</html>

```

Unit Calculation.aspx.cs

```

using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Net;
using System.IO;

```

```

using System.Data.SqlClient;

namespace ElectricityBill
{
    public partial class UnitCalculation : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        string z = "9790530960";
        SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection(System.Configuration.ConfigurationManager.ConnectionStrings["db"].ToString(
));
        protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            //if (!IsPostBack)
            //    ViewState["Count"] = 0;

            TextBox4.Text = Session["name"].ToString();
            TextBox3.Text = Session["unit"].ToString();
            TextBox2.Text = Session["mob"].ToString();

            int t1 = int.Parse(TextBox5.Text);
            int t2 = int.Parse(TextBox6.Text);
            int t3 = int.Parse(TextBox7.Text);
            int t4 = int.Parse(TextBox8.Text);
            int t5 = int.Parse(TextBox9.Text);

            int calc = t1 + t2+ t3 + t4 + t5;
            TextBox1.Text = calc.ToString();
            if (!IsPostBack)
            {
                t1 = 0;
                t2 = 0;
                t3 = 0;
                t4 = 0;
                t5 = 0;
            }

            }
            static int e1 = 0;
            static int e2 = 0;
            static int e3 = 0;
            static int e4 = 0;
            static int e5 = 0;

            protected void ImageButton1_Click(object sender, ImageClickEventArgs e)
            {

```

```

    Timer1.Enabled = true;
    string y = "You Have Consumed More Than 50% Of Electricity In This Month Try To
Reduce... Your Usage" + TextBox1.Text + "Units";
    con.Open();
    SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update Unit set Fan=" + TextBox5.Text + "",
con);
    cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
    con.Close();
    TextBox4.Text = Session["name"].ToString();
    TextBox3.Text = Session["unit"].ToString();
    TextBox2.Text = Session["mob"].ToString();
    int unit = int.Parse(TextBox3.Text);
    int tot = unit / 2;

    //ViewState["count"] = Convert.ToInt32(ViewState["count"]) + 2;
    //TextBox1.Text = ViewState["count"].ToString();
    int userVal = int.Parse(TextBox1.Text);
    if (userVal >= tot)
    {
        sendmessage(TextBox2.Text, y);
    }
}

protected void ImageButton2_Click(object sender, ImageClickEventArgs e)
{
    Timer2.Enabled = true;
    con.Open();
    SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update Unit set Fridge=" + TextBox6.Text +
"", con);
    cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
    con.Close();
    string y = "You Have Consumed More Than 50% Of Electricity In This Month Try To
Reduce... Your Usage" + TextBox1.Text + "Units";
    TextBox4.Text = Session["name"].ToString();
    TextBox3.Text = Session["unit"].ToString();
    TextBox2.Text = Session["mob"].ToString();
    int unit = int.Parse(TextBox3.Text);
    int tot = unit / 2;

    //ViewState["count"] = Convert.ToInt32(ViewState["count"]) + 5;
    //TextBox1.Text = ViewState["count"].ToString();
    int userVal = int.Parse(TextBox1.Text);
    if (userVal >= tot)
    {
        sendmessage(TextBox2.Text, y);
    }
}

```

```

    }

protected void ImageButton3_Click(object sender, ImageClickEventArgs e)
{
    Timer3.Enabled = true;
    con.Open();
    SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update Unit set AC=" + TextBox7.Text + "",
con);
    cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
    con.Close();
    string y = "You Have Consumed More Than 50% Of Electricity In This Month Try To
Reduce... Your Usage" + TextBox1.Text + "Units";
    TextBox4.Text = Session["name"].ToString();
    TextBox3.Text = Session["unit"].ToString();
    TextBox2.Text = Session["mob"].ToString();
    int unit = int.Parse(TextBox3.Text);
    int tot = unit / 2;

    //ViewState["count"] = Convert.ToInt32(ViewState["count"]) + 10;
    //TextBox1.Text = ViewState["count"].ToString();
    int userVal = int.Parse(TextBox1.Text);
    if (userVal >= tot)
    {
        sendmessage(TextBox2.Text, y);
    }
}

protected void ImageButton4_Click(object sender, ImageClickEventArgs e)
{
    Timer4.Enabled = true;
    con.Open();
    SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update Unit set TV=" + TextBox8.Text + "",
con);
    cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
    con.Close();
    string y = "You Have Consumed More Than 50% Of Electricity In This Month Try To
Reduce... Your Usage" + TextBox1.Text + "Units";
    TextBox4.Text = Session["name"].ToString();
    TextBox3.Text = Session["unit"].ToString();
    TextBox2.Text = Session["mob"].ToString();
    int unit = int.Parse(TextBox3.Text);
    int tot = unit / 2;

    //ViewState["count"] = Convert.ToInt32(ViewState["count"]) + 4;
    //TextBox1.Text = ViewState["count"].ToString();
    int userVal = int.Parse(TextBox1.Text);

```

```

        if (userVal >= tot)
        {
            sendmessage(TextBox2.Text, y);
        }
    }

protected void ImageButton5_Click(object sender, ImageClickEventArgs e)
{
    Timer5.Enabled = true;
    con.Open();
    SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update Unit set Mixie="" + TextBox9.Text + """,
con);
    cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
    con.Close();
    string y = "You Have Consumed More Than 50% Of Electricity In This Month Try To
Reduce Your Usage Unit Is " + TextBox1.Text;
    TextBox4.Text = Session["name"].ToString();
    TextBox3.Text = Session["unit"].ToString();
    TextBox2.Text = Session["mob"].ToString();
    int unit = int.Parse(TextBox3.Text);
    int tot = unit / 2;

    //ViewState["count"] = Convert.ToInt32(ViewState["count"]) + 3;
    //TextBox1.Text = ViewState["count"].ToString();
    int userVal = int.Parse(TextBox1.Text);
    if (userVal >= tot)
    {
        sendmessage(TextBox2.Text, y);
    }
}

protected void ImageButton6_Click(object sender, ImageClickEventArgs e)
{
}

protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    Session["name"] = TextBox1.Text;
    Response.Redirect("PayBill.aspx");
}

public void sendmessage(string targetno, string message)
{
    String query = "http://pay4sms.in/sendsms/?token=
b81edee36bcef4ddbba6ef535f8db03e&credit=2&sender=
RandDC&message=testsms&number=919150028012=" + targetno + "&message=" + message;

```

```

        //string query = "
http://bulksms.mysmsmantra.com:8080/WebSMS/SMSAPI.jsp?username=OculusTech&password=1526762373&sendername=OCULUS&mobilenos=" + targetno + "&message=" + message;
        WebClient client = new WebClient();
        Stream sin = client.OpenRead(query);
        Response.Write("<script language=javascript>alert('successfully Message
Send')</script>");
    }

    protected void Timer1_Tick(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        TextBox5.Text = e1.ToString();
        e1 = e1 + 3;
    }
    protected void Timer2_Tick(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        TextBox6.Text = e2.ToString();
        e2 = e2 + 5;
    }
    protected void Timer3_Tick(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        TextBox7.Text = e3.ToString();
        e3 = e3 + 10;
    }
    protected void Timer4_Tick(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        TextBox8.Text = e4.ToString();
        e4 = e4 + 6;
    }
    protected void Timer5_Tick(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        TextBox9.Text = e5.ToString();
        e5 = e5 + 4;
    }

    protected void ImageButton6_Click1(object sender, ImageClickEventArgs e)
    {
        Timer1.Enabled = false;
        con.Open();
        SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update Unit set Fan=" + TextBox5.Text + "",
con);
        cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
        con.Close();
    }

    protected void ImageButton7_Click(object sender, ImageClickEventArgs e)

```

```

    {
        Timer2.Enabled = false;
        con.Open();
        SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update Unit set Fridge=" + TextBox6.Text +
        """, con);
        cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
        con.Close();
    }

protected void ImageButton8_Click(object sender, ImageClickEventArgs e)
{
    Timer3.Enabled = false;
    con.Open();
    SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update Unit set AC=" + TextBox7.Text + """,
con);
    cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
    con.Close();
}

protected void ImageButton9_Click(object sender, ImageClickEventArgs e)
{
    Timer4.Enabled = false;
    con.Open();
    SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update Unit set TV=" + TextBox8.Text + """,
con);
    cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
    con.Close();
}

protected void ImageButton10_Click(object sender, ImageClickEventArgs e)
{
    Timer5.Enabled = false;
    con.Open();
    SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update Unit set Mixie=" + TextBox9.Text + """,
con);
    cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
    con.Close();
}
}
}

```

Usage Request.aspx

```

<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="UsageRequest.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ElectricityBill.UsageRequest" %>

```

```
<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
```

```
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
  <title>Smart Electricity</title>
  <meta name="description" content="website description" />
  <meta name="keywords" content="website keywords, website keywords" />
  <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" />
  <link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="style/style.css" title="style" />
  <style type="text/css">
    .style1
    {
      width: 97%;
      height: 211px;
    }
  </style>
</head>
<body>
  <div id="main">
    <div id="header">
      <div id="logo">
        <div id="logo_text">
          <!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->
          <h1><a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>
          <h2></h2>
        </div>
      </div>
      <div id="menubar">
        <ul id="menu">
          <!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're
on -->
          <li class="selected"><a href="FixedUnit.aspx">Fixed Unit</a></li>
          <li><a href="UnitCalculation.aspx">Meter Box</a></li>
          <li><a href="PayBill.aspx">Electricity Bill</a></li>
          <li><a href="UsageRequest.aspx">Usage Request</a></li>
          <li><a href="UserReview.aspx">User Review</a></li>
          <li><a href="UserLogin.aspx">Logout</a></li>
        </ul>
      </div>
    </div>
    <div id="site_content">

    <div id="content">
```

```

<form id="form1" runat="server">
<div>

    <br />
    <br />
    <asp:Label ID="Label1" runat="server" Font-Bold="True" Font-Size="X-Large"
        ForeColor="#0066FF"
        Text="GET YOUR ELECTRICITY USAGE REPORT FOR THIS
MONTH"></asp:Label>
    <br />
    <br />
    <table align="center" class="style1">
        <tr>
            <td>
                <asp:Label ID="Label2" runat="server" Text="NAME"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox1" runat="server" Height="30px"
Width="140px"></asp:TextBox>
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <td>
                <asp:Label ID="Label3" runat="server" Text="EB NUMBER"></asp:Label>
            </td>
            <td>
                <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox2" runat="server" Height="30px"
Width="140px"></asp:TextBox>
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <td>
                &nbsp;   </td>
            <td>
                <asp:Button ID="Button1" runat="server" Height="34px" onclick="Button1_Click"
                Text="GET REPORT" Width="104px" ForeColor="Red" />
            </td>
        </tr>
    </table>
    <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox3" runat="server" ReadOnly="True" Visible="False"
        Width="16px"></asp:TextBox>
    <asp:Label ID="Label4" runat="server" Text="Label"></asp:Label>
    <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox4" runat="server" ReadOnly="True" Visible="False"
        Width="16px"></asp:TextBox>
    <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox5" runat="server" ReadOnly="True" Visible="False"

```

```

        Width="16px"></asp:TextBox>
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox6" runat="server" ReadOnly="True" Visible="False"
            Width="16px"></asp:TextBox>
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox7" runat="server" ReadOnly="True" Visible="False"
            Width="16px"></asp:TextBox>
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox8" runat="server" ReadOnly="True" Visible="False"
            Width="16px"></asp:TextBox>
    <br />
    <br />

</div>
</form>
</div>
</div>
<div id="footer">
    Copyright &copy; Electric |
</div>
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

Usage Request.aspx.cs

```

using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Data.SqlClient;
using System.Net;
using System.IO;

namespace ElectricityBill
{
    public partial class UsageRequest : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        SqlConnection con = new
        SqlConnection(System.Configuration.ConfigurationManager.ConnectionStrings["db"].ToString(
        ));
        protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {

```

```

    }

protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    TextBox3.Text = Session["mob"].ToString();

    con.Open();
    SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("select * from Unit ", con);
    SqlDataReader dr = cmd.ExecuteReader();
    if (dr.Read())
    {

        TextBox4.Text = dr["Fan"].ToString();
        TextBox5.Text = dr["Fridge"].ToString();
        TextBox6.Text = dr["AC"].ToString();
        TextBox7.Text = dr["TV"].ToString();
        TextBox8.Text = dr["Mixie"].ToString();
    }
    string y = "In This Month Your Electricity Usage Fan=" + TextBox4.Text + "Units,
Fridge=" + TextBox5.Text + "Units, AC=" + TextBox6.Text + "Units, TV=" + TextBox7.Text
+ "Units, Mixie=" + TextBox8.Text + "Units Try To Reduce Dont Waste Electricity";
    sendmessage(TextBox3.Text, y);
}

public void sendmessage(string targetno, string message)
{
    String query = "http://pay4sms.in/sendsms/?token=
b81edee36bcef4ddbbaa6ef535f8db03e&credit=2&sender=
RandDC&message=testsms&number=919150028012=" + targetno + "&message=" + message;
    //string query = "
http://bulksms.mysmsmantra.com:8080/WebSMS/SMSAPI.jsp?username=OculusTech&passwo
rd=1526762373&sendername=OCULUS&mobilen=" + targetno + "&message=" + message;
    WebClient client = new WebClient();
    Stream sin = client.OpenRead(query);
    Response.Write("<script language=javascript>alert('successfully Reports
Send')</script>");
}
}
}
}

```

User Approval.aspx

```

<% @ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="UserApproval.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ElectricityBill.UserApproval" %>

```

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
  <title>Smart Electricity</title>
  <meta name="description" content="website description" />
  <meta name="keywords" content="website keywords, website keywords" />
  <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" />
  <link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="style/style.css" title="style" />
  <style type="text/css">

tbody{ background:transparent;border:0 none;font-
size:100%;margin:0;padding:0;border:0;outline:0;vertical-align:top;}
tr{ background:transparent;border:0 none;font-
size:100%;margin:0;padding:0;border:0;outline:0;vertical-align:top;}
table td:first-child { font-weight:bold;}

table td { padding:9px 10px 8px 20px;
  text-align: left;
}
table td { padding:0;border:none;border-collapse:collapse;}
  .style1
  {
    height: 63px;
  }
  .style2
  {
    height: 35px;
  }
</style>
</head>
<body>
<div id="main">
  <div id="header">
    <div id="logo">
      <div id="logo_text">
        <!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->
        <h1><a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>
        <h2></h2>
      </div>
    </div>
  <div id="menubar">
    <ul id="menu">

```

on -->

```
<!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're
on -->
<li class="selected"><a href="UserApproval.aspx">User Approval</a></li>
<li><a href="ViewUsers.aspx">View Users</a></li>
<li><a href="ViewPayment.aspx">View Payment</a></li>
<li><a href="ViewReports.aspx">View Reports</a></li>
<li><a href="AdminLogin.aspx">Logout</a></li>
```

```
</ul>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div id="site_content">
```

```
<div id="content">
```

```
<form id="form1" runat="server">
```

```
<div>
```

```
<br />
```

```
<br />
```

```
<asp:Label ID="Label1" runat="server" Font-Bold="True" Font-Size="X-Large"
ForeColor="#0066FF" Text="VIEW USER DETAILS"></asp:Label>
```

```
<br />
```

```
<br />
```

```
<br />
```

```
<table class="noborders">
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<td colspan="2">
```

```
&nbsp;   </td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<td class="style1">
```

```
<asp:Label ID="Label3" runat="server" Text="New User"></asp:Label>
```

```
<asp:DropDownList ID="DropDownList1" runat="server">
```

```
</asp:DropDownList>
```

```
<asp:Button ID="Button1" runat="server" BackColor="#999999" Height="34px"
onclick="Button1_Click" Text="VIEW" Width="94px" />
```

```
<asp:Button ID="Button4" runat="server" BackColor="#999999" Height="34px"
onclick="Button4_Click" Text="Clear All" Width="94px" />
```

```
</td>
```

```
<td class="style1">
```

```
</td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<td colspan="2">
```



```
<div id="footer">
    Copyright &copy; Electric |
</div>
</div>
</body>
</html>
```

User Approval.aspx.cs

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Data.SqlClient;
using System.Configuration;
using System.Data;

namespace ElectricityBill
{
    public partial class UserApproval : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        SqlConnection con = new
        SqlConnection(ConfigurationManager.ConnectionStrings["db"].ToString());
        protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            con.Open();
            SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("select * from register where
            Status='NotApproved'", con);
            SqlDataReader dr = cmd.ExecuteReader();
            while (dr.Read())
            {
                DropDownList1.Items.Add(dr["Username"].ToString());
            }
            con.Close();
        }
        protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("select Name as Name, Address as Address ,
            EbNumber as EbNumber , Mobileno as Mobileno from register where Status='NotApproved'",
            con);
            SqlDataAdapter dr = new SqlDataAdapter(cmd);
            DataSet ds = new DataSet();
```

```

        dr.Fill(ds, "register");
        GridView1.DataSource = ds;
        GridView1.DataMember = "register";
        GridView1.DataBind();
        con.Close();
    }
    protected void Button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        con.Open();
        SqlCommand cmd1 = new SqlCommand("update register set Status='Approved' where
Username="" + DropDownList1.Text + """, con);
        cmd1.ExecuteNonQuery();
        con.Close();
        Response.Write("<script>alert('Given Authority ... ')</script>");
        con.Open();
    }
    protected void Button3_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        con.Open();
        SqlCommand cmd1 = new SqlCommand("update register set Status='NotApproved'
where Username="" + DropDownList1.Text + """, con);
        cmd1.ExecuteNonQuery();
        con.Close();
        Response.Write("<script>alert('Decline User ... ')</script>");
        con.Open();
    }
    protected void Button4_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        con.Open();
        SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("delete from register ", con);
        cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
        con.Close();
        Response.Write("<script>alert('Delete data Successfully ')</script>");
    }
}
}
}

```

User Login.aspx

```

<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="UserLogin.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ElectricityBill.UserLogin" %>

```

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">

```

```

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
  <title>Smart Electricity</title>
  <meta name="description" content="website description" />
  <meta name="keywords" content="website keywords, website keywords" />
  <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" />
  <link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="style/style.css" title="style" />
  <style type="text/css">
    .style1
    {
      width: 97%;
      height: 211px;
    }
  </style>
</head>
<body>
  <div id="main">
    <div id="header">
      <div id="logo">
        <div id="logo_text">
          <!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->
          <h1><a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>
          <h2></h2>
        </div>
      </div>
      <div id="menubar">
        <ul id="menu">
          <!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're
on -->
          <li class="selected"><a href="index.html">Home</a></li>
          <li><a href="AdminLogin.aspx">Admin Login</a></li>
          <li><a href="UserLogin.aspx">User Login</a></li>
          <li><a href="Registration.aspx">Registration</a></li>
        </ul>
      </div>
    </div>
    <div id="site_content">
      <div id="content">
        <form id="form1" runat="server">
        <div>
          <br />

```



```
</body>
</html>
```

User Login.aspx.cs

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

namespace ElectricityBill
{
    public partial class UserLogin : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection(System.Configuration.ConfigurationManager.ConnectionStrings["db"].ToString(
));
        protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {

        }

        protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            con.Open();
            SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("select * from register where Username='" +
TextBox1.Text + "' and Password='" + TextBox2.Text + "' and status='Approved' ", con);

            SqlDataReader reader = cmd.ExecuteReader();
            if (reader.Read())
            {
                Response.Redirect("FixedUnit.aspx");
            }
            else
            {
                Response.Write("<script>alert('Unathourized User please Contact Your Admin
')</script>");
            }
        }
    }
}
```

User Review.aspx

```
<% @ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="UserReview.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ElectricityBill.UserReview" %>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
```

```
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
  <title>Smart Electricity</title>
  <meta name="description" content="website description" />
  <meta name="keywords" content="website keywords, website keywords" />
  <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" />
  <link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="style/style.css" title="style" />
  <style type="text/css">
    .style1
    {
      width: 97%;
      height: 211px;
    }
  </style>
</head>
<body>
  <div id="main">
    <div id="header">
      <div id="logo">
        <div id="logo_text">
          <!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->
          <h1><a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>
          <h2></h2>
        </div>
      </div>
      <div id="menubar">
        <ul id="menu">
          <!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're
on -->
          <li class="selected"><a href="FixedUnit.aspx">Fixed Unit</a></li>
          <li><a href="UnitCalculation.aspx">Meter Box</a></li>
          <li><a href="PayBill.aspx">Electricity Bill</a></li>
          <li><a href="UsageRequest.aspx">Usage Request</a></li>
          <li><a href="UserReview.aspx">User Review</a></li>
          <li><a href="UserLogin.aspx">Logout</a></li>
        </ul>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</body>
</html>
```

```

</div>
</div>
<div id="site_content">

  <div id="content">

<form id="form1" runat="server">
<div>

  <br />
  <br />
  <asp:Label ID="Label1" runat="server" Font-Bold="True" Font-Size="X-Large"
    ForeColor="#0066FF" Text="TELL YOUR EXPERIENCE ABOUT OUR
SERVICE"></asp:Label>
  <br />
  <br />
  <table align="center" class="style1">
    <tr>
      <td>
        <asp:Label ID="Label2" runat="server" Text="NAME"></asp:Label>
      </td>
      <td>
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox1" runat="server" Height="30px"
Width="140px"></asp:TextBox>
      </td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
      <td>
        <asp:Label ID="Label3" runat="server" Text="FEEDBACK"></asp:Label>
      </td>
      <td>
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox2" runat="server" Height="54px" Width="168px"
TextMode="MultiLine"></asp:TextBox>
      </td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
      <td>
        &nbsp;</td>
      <td>
        <asp:Button ID="Button1" runat="server" Height="34px" onclick="Button1_Click"
Text="REVIEW" Width="82px" />
      </td>
    </tr>
  </table>
  <asp:Label ID="Label4" runat="server" Text="Label"></asp:Label>
  <br />

```

```

        <br />

    </div>
</form>
</div>
</div>
<div id="footer">
    Copyright &copy; Electric |
</div>
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

User Review.aspx.cs

```

using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Data.SqlClient;
using System.Configuration;

namespace ElectricityBill
{
    public partial class UserReview : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection(ConfigurationManager.ConnectionStrings["db"].ToString());
        protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            TextBox2.Text = Session["mob"].ToString();
        }

        protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            con.Open();
            SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("insert into report values('" + TextBox1.Text +
"', '" + TextBox2.Text + "')", con);
            cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
            con.Close();
            Response.Write("<script>alert('Your Feedback send ... Thank You ')</script>");
        }
    }
}

```

```
}  
}  
}
```

View Payment.aspx

```
<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="ViewPayment.aspx.cs"  
Inherits="ElectricityBill.ViewPayment" %>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"  
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
```

```
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">  
<head id="Head1" runat="server">  
  <title>Smart Electricity</title>  
  <meta name="description" content="website description" />  
  <meta name="keywords" content="website keywords, website keywords" />  
  <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" />  
  <link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="style/style.css" title="style" />  
</head>  
<body>  
  <div id="main">  
    <div id="header">  
      <div id="logo">  
        <div id="logo_text">  
          <!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->  
          <h1><a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span  
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>  
          <h2></h2>  
        </div>  
      </div>  
      <div id="menubar">  
        <ul id="menu">  
          <!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're  
on -->  
          <li class="selected"><a href="UserApproval.aspx">User Approval</a></li>  
          <li><a href="ViewUsers.aspx">View Users</a></li>  
          <li><a href="ViewPayment.aspx">View Payment</a></li>  
          <li><a href="ViewReports.aspx">View Reports</a></li>  
          <li><a href="AdminLogin.aspx">Logout</a></li>  
  
        </ul>  
      </div>  
    </div>  
  </div>  
<div id="site_content">
```

```

<div id="content">

<form id="form1" runat="server">
<div>

<br />
<br />
<asp:Label ID="Label1" runat="server" Font-Bold="True" Font-Size="X-Large"
  ForeColor="#0066FF" Text="VIEW PAYMENT"></asp:Label>
<br />
<br />
<br />
<asp:GridView ID="GridView1" runat="server" Height="282px" Width="435px"
  AutoGenerateColumns="False" BackColor="White" BorderColor="#DEDFDE"
  BorderStyle="None" BorderWidth="1px" CellPadding="4"
  DataSourceID="SqlDataSource1" ForeColor="Black" GridLines="Vertical">
  <AlternatingRowStyle BackColor="White" />
  <Columns>
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Payment_Date" HeaderText="Payment_Date"
      SortExpression="Payment_Date" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="EB_number" HeaderText="EB_number"
      SortExpression="EB_number" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Name" HeaderText="Name" SortExpression="Name" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Phone" HeaderText="Phone" SortExpression="Phone"
  />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Unit" HeaderText="Unit" SortExpression="Unit" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Amount" HeaderText="Amount"
      SortExpression="Amount" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="CardType" HeaderText="CardType"
      SortExpression="CardType" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="CardNo" HeaderText="CardNo"
      SortExpression="CardNo" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Cvv" HeaderText="Cvv" SortExpression="Cvv" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="ExpiryDate" HeaderText="ExpiryDate"
      SortExpression="ExpiryDate" />
  </Columns>
  <FooterStyle BackColor="#CCCC99" />
  <HeaderStyle BackColor="#6B696B" Font-Bold="True" ForeColor="White" />
  <PagerStyle BackColor="#F7F7DE" ForeColor="Black" HorizontalAlign="Right" />
  <RowStyle BackColor="#F7F7DE" />
  <SelectedRowStyle BackColor="#CE5D5A" Font-Bold="True" ForeColor="White" />
  <SortedAscendingCellStyle BackColor="#FBFBF2" />
  <SortedAscendingHeaderStyle BackColor="#848384" />
  <SortedDescendingCellStyle BackColor="#EAEAD3" />
  <SortedDescendingHeaderStyle BackColor="#575357" />

```

```

</asp:GridView>
<asp:SqlDataSource ID="SqlDataSource1" runat="server"
  ConnectionString="<%$ ConnectionStrings:db %>"
  SelectCommand="SELECT * FROM [Payment]"></asp:SqlDataSource>
<br />

</div>
</form>
</div>
</div>
<div id="footer">
  Copyright &copy; Electric |
</div>
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

View Reports.aspx

```

<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="ViewReports.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ElectricityBill.ViewReports" %>

```

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
  <title>Smart Electricity</title>
  <meta name="description" content="website description" />
  <meta name="keywords" content="website keywords, website keywords" />
  <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" />
  <link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="style/style.css" title="style" />
</head>
<body>
<div id="main">
  <div id="header">
    <div id="logo">
      <div id="logo_text">
        <!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->
        <h1><a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>
        <h2></h2>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
  <div id="menubar">

```

```

    <ul id="menu">
      <!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're
on -->
      <li class="selected"><a href="UserApproval.aspx">User Approval</a></li>
      <li><a href="ViewUsers.aspx">View Users</a></li>
      <li><a href="ViewPayment.aspx">View Payment</a></li>
      <li><a href="ViewReports.aspx">View Reports</a></li>
      <li><a href="AdminLogin.aspx">Logout</a></li>

    </ul>
  </div>
</div>
<div id="site_content">

  <div id="content">

<form id="form1" runat="server">
<div>

  <br />
  <br />
  <asp:Label ID="Label1" runat="server" Font-Bold="True" Font-Size="X-Large"
    ForeColor="#0066FF" Text="VIEW REPORTS"></asp:Label>
  <br />
  <br />
  <br />
  <asp:GridView ID="GridView1" runat="server" Height="282px" Width="435px"
    AutoGenerateColumns="False" BackColor="White" BorderColor="#CC9966"
    BorderStyle="None" BorderWidth="1px" CellPadding="4" DataKeyNames="Id"
    DataSourceID="SqlDataSource1">
    <Columns>
      <asp:BoundField DataField="Id" HeaderText="Id" InsertVisible="False"
        ReadOnly="True" SortExpression="Id" />
      <asp:BoundField DataField="Name" HeaderText="Name" SortExpression="Name" />
      <asp:BoundField DataField="Feedback" HeaderText="Feedback"
        SortExpression="Feedback" />
    </Columns>
    <FooterStyle BackColor="#FFFFCC" ForeColor="#330099" />
    <HeaderStyle BackColor="#990000" Font-Bold="True" ForeColor="#FFFFCC" />
    <PagerStyle BackColor="#FFFFCC" ForeColor="#330099" HorizontalAlign="Center"
  />
    <RowStyle BackColor="White" ForeColor="#330099" />
    <SelectedRowStyle BackColor="#FFCC66" Font-Bold="True" ForeColor="#663399" />
    <SortedAscendingCellStyle BackColor="#FEECEB" />
    <SortedAscendingHeaderStyle BackColor="#AF0101" />
    <SortedDescendingCellStyle BackColor="#F6F0C0" />

```

```

        <SortedDescendingHeaderStyle BackColor="#7E0000" />
    </asp:GridView>
    <asp:SqlDataSource ID="SqlDataSource1" runat="server"
        ConnectionString="<%$ ConnectionStrings:db %>"
        SelectCommand="SELECT * FROM [report]"></asp:SqlDataSource>
    <br />

</div>
</form>
</div>
</div>
<div id="footer">
    Copyright &copy; Electric |
</div>
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

View Usage.aspx

```

<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeBehind="ViewUsers.aspx.cs"
Inherits="ElectricityBill.ViewUsers" %>

```

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
    <title>Smart Electricity</title>
    <meta name="description" content="website description" />
    <meta name="keywords" content="website keywords, website keywords" />
    <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=windows-1252" />
    <link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="style/style.css" title="style" />
</head>
<body>
<div id="main">
    <div id="header">
        <div id="logo">
            <div id="logo_text">
                <!-- class="logo_colour", allows you to change the colour of the text -->
                <h1><a href="index.html">Smart Electricity<span
class="logo_colour">Billing</span></a></h1>
                <h2></h2>
            </div>

```

```

</div>
<div id="menubar">
  <ul id="menu">
    <!-- put class="selected" in the li tag for the selected page - to highlight which page you're
on -->
    <li class="selected"><a href="UserApproval.aspx">User Approval</a></li>
    <li><a href="ViewUsers.aspx">View Users</a></li>
    <li><a href="ViewPayment.aspx">View Payment</a></li>
    <li><a href="ViewReports.aspx">View Reports</a></li>
    <li><a href="AdminLogin.aspx">Logout</a></li>

  </ul>
</div>
</div>
<div id="site_content">

  <div id="content">

<form id="form1" runat="server">
<div>

  <br />
  <br />
  <asp:Label ID="Label1" runat="server" Font-Bold="True" Font-Size="X-Large"
  ForeColor="#0066FF" Text="VIEW USERS"></asp:Label>
  <br />
  <br />
  <br />
  <asp:GridView ID="GridView1" runat="server" Height="282px" Width="435px"
  AutoGenerateColumns="False" CellPadding="4" DataSourceID="SqlDataSource1"
  ForeColor="#333333" GridLines="None">
  <AlternatingRowStyle BackColor="White" />
  <Columns>
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Name" HeaderText="Name" SortExpression="Name" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="FatherName" HeaderText="FatherName"
    SortExpression="FatherName" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="EbNumber" HeaderText="EbNumber"
    SortExpression="EbNumber" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="MobileNo" HeaderText="MobileNo"
    SortExpression="MobileNo" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="EmailID" HeaderText="EmailID"
    SortExpression="EmailID" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Address" HeaderText="Address"
    SortExpression="Address" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Username" HeaderText="Username"
    SortExpression="Username" />

```

```

        <asp:BoundField DataField="Password" HeaderText="Password"
            SortExpression="Password" />
        <asp:BoundField DataField="Status" HeaderText="Status"
            SortExpression="Status" />
    </Columns>
    <EditRowStyle BackColor="#7C6F57" />
    <FooterStyle BackColor="#1C5E55" Font-Bold="True" ForeColor="White" />
    <HeaderStyle BackColor="#1C5E55" Font-Bold="True" ForeColor="White" />
    <PagerStyle BackColor="#666666" ForeColor="White" HorizontalAlign="Center" />
    <RowStyle BackColor="#E3EAEB" />
    <SelectedRowStyle BackColor="#C5BBAF" Font-Bold="True" ForeColor="#333333"
/>
    <SortedAscendingCellStyle BackColor="#F8Fafa" />
    <SortedAscendingHeaderStyle BackColor="#246B61" />
    <SortedDescendingCellStyle BackColor="#D4DFE1" />
    <SortedDescendingHeaderStyle BackColor="#15524A" />
</asp:GridView>
<asp:SqlDataSource ID="SqlDataSource1" runat="server"
    ConnectionString="<%$ ConnectionStrings:db %>"
    SelectCommand="SELECT * FROM [register]"></asp:SqlDataSource>
<br />

</div>
</form>
</div>
</div>
<div id="footer">
    Copyright &copy; Electric |
</div>
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

7. TESTING

Testing is the major quality control measure employed during software development. Its basic function is to detect errors. Testing is the process of executing a program with the intention of finding errors. It is complete verification to detect whether the objective is met and the user requirements are satisfied. After the coding phase, testing is done to test the proper working of the new system. Testing represents the ultimate review of specification, design and coding. Thus the goal of testing is to uncover the requirements, design encoding errors in the program.

System testing is actually a series of different test whose primary purpose is to fully exercise the computer-based program.

Different types of testing are:

- Unit Testing
- Integration Testing
- Validation Testing

7.1. UNIT TESTING

Unit testing involves the design of test cases that validate the internal program logic is functioning properly, and that program input produces valid outputs. All decision branches and internal code flow should be validated. It is the testing of individual unit before integration. This is a structural testing, that relies on knowledge of its construction and is invasive. Unit test perform basic tests at component level and test a specific business process, application, and/or system configuration. Unit tests ensure that each unique path of a business process performs accurately to the documented specifications and contains clearly defined inputs and expected results. In the lines of this strategy all, the individual functions and modules were put to the independently. By following this strategy all, the errors in coding were identified and corrected.

Unit testing is a procedure used to validate the individual units of source code is working properly. The goal of unit testing is to isolate each part of the program and show that the individual parts are correct. A unit test provides a strict, written contract that the piece of code must satisfy. As a result, it affords server benefits.

Unit testing is typically done by software developers to ensure that the code they have written meets software requirements and behaves as the developer intended. Each unit of the system implemented in the source code is checked for correctness. All error-handling paths are tested. User authentication form and other each individual modules form are taken as independently. Here login and organization form are taken as smallest unit

S. No	Test Condition	Expected Result	Actual Result	Result
1.	Check whether the username and password provided by the customer matches each other.	It displays the message welcome to users.	It displays the message welcome user.	Success

S. No	Test Condition	Expected Result	Actual Result	Result
1.	Check whether the user fills all the columns.	It displays the message Registered success.	It displays the message Registered success.	Success

7.2. VALIDATION TESTING

Validation testing is done to validate the inputs given by the user. The user inputs are checked for their correctness and range. If there are errors, the error message is given and the user is prompted again to enter the new value. If the user types some characters in the numeric and an error message and it is demonstrated in the following figure.

TC.ID	Test Condition	Test Input	Expected Result	Actual Result	Result
VT-1.1	Check whether the username is empty in the login process	Empty field	It displays the error message as please enter username	It displays the error message as please enter username	Success
VT-1.2	Check whether the password is empty in the login process	Empty field	It displays the error message as please enter password.	It displays the error message as please enter password .	Success
VT-1.3	Check whether the username and password is incorrect	Incorrect username and password	It displays the error message as enter valid username and password	It displays the error message as enter valid username and password	Success

VT-1.4	Check whether username and password is matched	Incorrect username and password	It displays the error message as Please register first.	It displays the error message as Please register first.	Success
--------	--	---------------------------------	---	---	---------

7.3. INTEGRATION TESTING

Testing is done for each module. After testing all the modules, the modules are integrated and testing of the final system is done with the test data, specially designed to show that the system will operate successfully in all its aspects conditions. Thus the system testing is a confirmation that all is correct and an opportunity to show the user that the system works.

PAYMENT METHOD DETAILS	
PAYMENT DATE	1-20-2020
EB NUMBER	<input type="text"/>
NAME	<input type="text"/>
MOBILE NO	<input type="text"/>
UNIT	280
AMOUNT	1400
CARD TYPE	select ▾
CARD NO	<input type="text"/>
CVV	<input type="text"/>
EXP DATE	<input type="text"/> ...
<input type="button" value="PAY"/>	
Label	

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7.4 DEBUGGING

The program displays a string "We are debugging" to the user. Suppose when we run the application, for some reason, the string is not displayed. To identify the problem we need to add a breakpoint. We can add a breakpoint to the code line which displays the string. This breakpoint will pause the execution of the program. At this point, the programmer can see what is possibly going wrong.

Server Error in '/' Application.

Object reference not set to an instance of an object.

Description: An unhandled exception occurred during the execution of the current web request. Please review the stack trace for more information about the error and where it originated in the code.

Exception Details: System.NullReferenceException: Object reference not set to an instance of an object.

Source Error:

```
Line 20:         // ViewState["Count"] = 0;
Line 21:
Line 22:         TextBox4.Text = Session["name"].ToString();
Line 23:         TextBox3.Text = Session["unit"].ToString();
Line 24:         TextBox2.Text = Session["mob"].ToString();
```

Source File: D:\TAJUDEEN\ElectricityBill\ElectricityBill\UnitCalculation.aspx.cs **Line:** 22

Stack Trace:

```
[NullReferenceException: Object reference not set to an instance of an object.]
ElectricityBill.UnitCalculation.Page_Load(Object sender, EventArgs e) in D:\TAJUDEEN\ElectricityBill\ElectricityBill\UnitCalculation.aspx.cs:22
System.Web.Util.CalliEventHandlerDelegateProxy.Callback(Object sender, EventArgs e) +52
System.Web.UI.Control.OnLoad(EventArgs e) +97
System.Web.UI.Control.LoadRecursive() +61
System.Web.UI.Page.ProcessRequestMain(Boolean includeStagesBeforeAsyncPoint, Boolean includeStagesAfterAsyncPoint) +693
```

Version Information: Microsoft .NET Framework Version:4.0.30319; ASP.NET Version:4.0.3028.0

8. ACCEPTANCE TESTING

Acceptance testing can be defined in many ways, but a simple definition is the succeeds when the software functions in a manner that can be reasonable expected by the customer. After the acceptance test has been conducted, one of the two possible conditions exists. This is to fine whether the inputs are accepted by the database or other validations. For example accept only numbers in the numeric field, date format data in the date field. Also the null check for the not null fields. If any error occurs then show the error messages. The function of performance characteristics to specification and is accepted. A deviation from specification is uncovered and a deficiency list is created.

WHITE BOX TESTING

White box testing, sometimes called "Glass-box testing". Using white box testing methods, the following tests were made on the system,

- All independent paths with in a module have been exercised at least once.
- All logical decisions were checked for the true and false side of the values.
- All loops were executed to check their boundary values.
- Internal data-structure was tested for their validity.

BLACK BOX TESTING

Black box testing focuses on the functional requirements of the software. That is black box testing enables the software engineer to drive a set of input conditions that will fully exercise the requirements for a program. Black box testing is not an alternative for white box testing techniques. Rather, it is a complementary approach that is likely to uncover different class of errors. Black box testing attempts to find errors in the following categories:

- Interface errors.
- Performances in data structures or external database access.
- Performance errors.
- Initialization and termination errors.
- Incorrect or missing functions.

CONCLUSION

This Lower Electricity Bills at Home is window based applications which can be reducing the work in the particular Electricity Board for maintain the details as well as report generation. This software package can be operational in menu driven way which will be helpful to the end user. This project aims to move away from the traditional method of manual process of storing the details about electricity bill in which an individual has to physically record the reading. Administrative can view all the details in the Electricity board like employee details, consumer details, etc, and it has an efficient tool for search any result. Different types of reports can be obtained from the report menu. This system improves the performance of the EB which has facility to store the reading details, billing details of the particular service. The main advantage of this system is to reduce the work of the staff and reduce the time of the customer while waiting for paying bill. This process has the efficient mechanism to display customer details while enter the service number and also reduce the paper work while billing process. The success of the process is to maintain the details all related details in one application and has the efficient search operation. There is possible to generate the report in all the dimensions of the details. Further the extension of the process is obtain a web based application which will help to the user can view their bill details and also allow the customer for online payment of their EB Bill amount.

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